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Implementation of smart factories for automation and optimization of agricultural production

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Introducing smart factories in agriculture is critical since such technologies help solve key problems such as food shortages and adaptation to climate change and open new perspectives for sustainable and efficient agriculture.

The article aimed to examine the features of smart factory adoption at the present stage of global agricultural development.

Materials and Methods. The materials were articles from peer-reviewed scientific journals on industrial technology, industrial automation, and economics. The case method was applied, i.e., a detailed analysis of a case study of smart factory implementation to understand the challenges faced by the enterprise and the success factors.

Research Findings. A remarkable case study on successful implementation of smart factories in agricultural production, the California Company for Sustainable Agriculture project, was considered. Implementing new technologies significantly increased crop yields by 15-20% compared to traditional methods. Optimization of water, fertilizer, and energy use resulted in a 30-40% cost reduction.

Conclusion. Implementing smart factory in agricultural production has great potential to improve the productivity and sustainability of the agro sector.

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FOR CITATION

INTRODUCTION

Implementing smart factory in agriculture is relevant due to several reasons related to global challenges and changes in the agricultural sector. The world population is predicted to reach 9-10 billion by 2050; this requires a significant increase in food production. Climatic changes cause heterogeneity in agricultural conditions, such as droughts, floods, and changing temperature patterns.

Advances in digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, and artificial intelligence are opening up new opportunities to increase productivity. Adopting innovative factory technologies can significantly reduce production costs by automating processes, reducing wastage, and improving product quality; this makes businesses more sustainable and profitable.

Management of modern agriculture is complex and multifaceted. Smart farms allow integration of different aspects (agronomy, logistics, finance) into a single system, which improves the manageability and predictability of the result.

Thus, the relevance of implementing smart factories in agriculture is undeniable, since these technologies not only contribute to solving pressing problems such as food shortages and climate resilience but also create new opportunities for sustainable and efficient agriculture.

The paper examines the specifics of smart factory adoption at the present stage of global agricultural development.

Literature review

Smart factories are more adaptive, efficient and sustainable than traditional production plants, which is a key factor in today's market conditions.

Chandra Sekaran S. et al. define digital factories and their differences from other similar concepts such as smart factories, CPS, and virtual factories. The authors emphasize the need to use virtual reality (VR) to model a digital factory that helps in decision-making and efficient operation of a manufacturing facility [1].

As written by X. Zhang & X. Ming, various countries issued policies on intelligent manufacturing and put forward the corresponding system architecture, including its hierarchy and constituent elements. However, from their point of view, the relationship between the framework's elements and specific application scenarios should be further expanded and explored. The paper's authors provide guidelines for enterprises to implement the scheme and phases of intelligent manufacturing [2].

According to W. K. Jung et al., it is difficult for SMEs to implement innovative factory technologies due to financial and technical difficulties. The authors aim to build a smart factory

that can be easily operated at a low cost. The authors reviewed a case study on quality control for small and medium-sized apparel manufacturing companies [3].

The research mostly focuses on key technical issues related to operating smart factories: architecture, automation, data processing and protection, etc.

Thus J. Gao et al. developed a medium access control protocol characterized by gratuitous distributed channel access to support high device density and low communication delay with low communication overhead. The author's design shows promising potential for smart factories while providing mass connectivity and millisecond-level network latency for high-priority devices [4].

D. G. Park et al. find that existing switching control protocols are insufficient for smart factories' switching support. The SFSH service handoff method proposed by the authors utilizes the location and delay information of device switching signals in the factory to support mobility management and improve switching performance in wireless networks [5].

G. Baranwal & D. P. Vidyarthi write that local servers in smart factories are usually not equipped with sufficient processing power to handle all types of computational tasks. Therefore, some tasks need to be offloaded to a higher layer such as the cloud. The authors propose an offloading decision model using game theory [6].

S. Jung & J. Kim propose a two-stage large-scale surveillance algorithm for industrial smart ports and logistics platforms. The authors utilize drones, an algorithm to work between them, and systems for peripheral computing [7].

E. Yildiz et al. believe that the concept of a virtual factory (VF) based on a digital twin as an integrated simulation model of a factory, including its subsystems, is promising to support manufacturing organizations in adapting to dynamic and complex environments [8].

According to S. Z. Tan & M. E. Labastida, different vendors, protocols, and technologies hinder the development as their implementation requires a high level of training and specialized knowledge that may not be available. The authors propose a unified cloud platform to solve interoperability problems using service-oriented architecture (SOA) in a cloud platform [9].

P. Zorić et al. write that Smart Factory has a complex information and communication infrastructure and potentially more significant security threats and risks it faces. The rapid development of the Smart Factory environment dictates the need for secure interactions between the elements of the production system [10].

K. J. Yi & Y. S. Jeong investigate the components of the core architecture of a Smart Factory and discuss security issues and challenges that may arise before the establishment of a Smart Factory. The authors propose a Smart Factory security model and algorithms for behavior in case of cyber attacks [11].

Implementing Smart Factory in agricultural enterprises (or agro-smart factories) represents transformation of production, management and distribution using modern technologies.

Thus, S. Ragaveena et al. discuss different types of soilless farming, their advantages over conventional soil methods, various types of sensors used in agriculture, and adoption of latest technologies in soilless farming [12].

Y. He wrote that advances in artificial light for plant growth have allowed growing crops on no-till land such as skyscrapers, deserts, islands, etc. [13].

Z. Zheng et al. point out that with the development of sensor equipment and machine learning technology, intelligent agriculture becomes an important direction for transforming traditional agriculture. The authors proposed a deep learning algorithm with reinforcement learning to improve crop productivity, particularly optimizing sugar beet yield [14].

C. Hyunjin & H. Sainan write about the need to use the Internet of Things and AI to analyze the optimal growing conditions of various crops in rural and urban areas [15].

Thus, the scientific challenge of implementing smart factories in agricultural production lies in several factors affecting the efficiency, sustainability, and scalability of agro-smart technologies.

Agriculture is often dependent on specific climatic conditions. Developing technologies adapting to different regions and climate zones is a significant scientific challenge. The biological characteristics of various crops and livestock processes need to be considered, which requires specialized solutions.

The scientific problem is to develop effective methods for collecting, processing, and analyzing large amounts of data from sensors, drones, and other sources.

It is necessary to develop methods for assessing the economic feasibility of implementing a 'smart factory', including both direct and hidden costs. Separately, support mechanisms for small and medium-sized agricultural enterprises are required for implementing new technologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were articles from peer-reviewed scientific journals on industrial technology, industrial automation, and economics: International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing, Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing, Journal of Real-Time Image Processing, Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology, Nanotechnology for Environmental Engineering, Multimedia Tools and Applications and others.

Literature related to smart factories, the 4th industrial revolution, and modern manufacturing and innovation management technologies was also used.

The case method, i.e., a detailed case study of smart factory implementation, was used as a research method to understand the challenges faced by the company and success factors.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Digitalization of enterprises involves introducing information technology to all areas of an organization. It is a necessary factor in maintaining the position of entrepreneurship and in allowing new opportunities for developing and improving production and management. Flexible adaptation to changing economic conditions increases. Digital technologies allow for acceleration and qualitatively update production and the product itself, significantly expanding the service areas in meeting customers' needs, setting ambitious goals, and achieving strategic objectives. A valid reason for introducing digital technologies into business operations is customer requirements. In parallel, a significant cost reduction of all available resources is required, and specialized digital technologies are used to help save them.

Digitalization of enterprises also involves creating digital platforms which help achieve a flexible change of direction in producing goods and services, maximum cooperation, and synchronization of all processes in a single information space.

Replacing traditional business methods with digital technologies allows for a successful digital transformation of the enterprise. In the structure of a digital enterprise, approaches and methods of managing production change; as part of these processes, all types of project management are modernized, including investments in intellectual capital formation. A significant place in creating an intelligent enterprise is given to cybersecurity issues because, on the scale of the global economic community, intellectualization of production goes hand in hand with a new phenomenon – cyberterrorism. High cost of digital products and the corresponding digital tools and equipment that organizations have to purchase to ensure technological leaps in the production of goods and services and to ensure the information security of enterprises is becoming disastrous for business owners. At the same time, individual enterprises are extremely slowly and unevenly equipped with modern technologies equipment and software.

Analytical studies conducted on digital transformation of production show that enterprises using new digital technologies and new management methods are 26% more profitable on average than their competitors [16].

Every day, enterprises are growing dynamically while actively experiencing increased competition, and to successfully promote their business endeavors, they need to create an intelligent enterprise. It allows using the results of digital factories, partially or entirely replacing humans with AI. Virtualization of enterprises allows for covering all resources, from raw materials to the final product and its delivery to the consumer.

The features of the 'smart enterprise' are:

- data storage in cloud services;
- data collection with the help of sensors and transducers;
- processing information is based on specific algorithms that allow optimizing work;
- production with almost no human involvement by creating human-machine interfaces and a digital platform;
- redistribution of production, based on creating individual consumer orders providing resource savings [17].

Digital technologies and new management approaches within the framework of doing business contribute to maintaining the competitiveness of industrial enterprises in the market and expanding their capabilities [18].

The digitalization market aims to automate an enterprise's major and minor business processes. Among the tools of digitalization using RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technologies are:

- Big Data analytics,
- artificial intelligence,
- cloud technologies,
- adaptation of production operating costs,
- machine learning,
- formation of various systems in redistributing enterprise resources [19], including personnel management.

A vivid example of successful implementation of smart factories in agricultural production is the California Sustainable Agriculture project – the company uses modern technology to implement a precision farming system on its farms. Sensors and IoT devices monitor soil and plant conditions in real-time, recording moisture levels, temperature, and nutrient content. The collected data is analyzed through powerful analytics platforms, allowing farmers to decide when to irrigate, fertilize, and harvest. Directing data to cloud-based systems can be processed using machine learning algorithms to predict outcomes.

To monitor field conditions, company employees use drones that take aerial photos; the data helps determine the need for specific agronomic actions, such as spraying pesticides or fertilizers. The farms also implement automatic irrigation systems that respond to data from

sensors, thus significantly reducing water consumption by optimizing irrigation processes depending on the current needs of the plants. Climate change adaptation station technologies are used to monitor opportunities to improve resilience and reduce risks associated with changing weather conditions.

As a result, yields increased significantly by 15-20% compared to traditional methods, and optimization of resource use (water, fertilizer, and energy) resulted in 30-40% cost reduction. Moreover, reduced use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, as well as efficient water management, improved the environmental situation on the farms.

This example demonstrates how implementing a smart factory and modern technologies can not only improve the economic efficiency of agricultural production and make it more sustainable and environmentally friendly – such solutions can serve as a model for other farmers and businesses looking to optimize their processes.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thus, further implementation of smart factories in agricultural production is quite promising. In particular, it concerns the further development of the Internet of Things. The number of sensors and devices connected to the internet will continue to grow, and this will provide more accurate crop, soil, and environmental monitoring.

AI algorithms will make it possible to analyze large amounts of data, enabling more accurate forecasts of crop yields, threats, and optimal time for agronomic operations.

Innovative technologies will help farmers better adapt to changing climatic conditions, allowing them to predict water and nutrient needs accurately.

Adopting technologies for sustainable resource management allows for efficient water use, biodiversity and reduced environmental impacts.

Regarding management efficiency, increasing automation in agronomic processes such as planting, harvesting, and cultivation can reduce labor costs and increase productivity.

Creating and implementing training programs for agronomists and farmers on the use of new technologies and systems will maximize opportunities offered by smart farming. Here, we are close to the viewpoint of J. W. Kim et al., who write that students and practitioners have difficulties understanding the concepts, elements, and features of the whole innovative factory system [20]. It is essential to encourage young professionals, i.e., attract them to agronomy through internship programs and research grants.

The economic benefits of implementing smart factories in agricultural production should be emphasized. By optimizing processes and efficient use of resources, farmers can reduce their costs, which will increase profits significantly.

Thus, implementing smart factories in agricultural production has great potential to improve the productivity and sustainability of the agribusiness sector.

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